

Challenges and Opportunities for Biodiversity Conservation and Sustainable Development of Ecotourism in Lalzi Bay, Durres County, Albania - Today's Science for Tomorrow's Management.

A Methodology Guide with a Concrete Example by Lalzi Bay, Durres County, Albania

Arnisa Lushaj, Arvjen Lushaj, Sunitha N. Seenappa, Georgia Butina-Watson, Bashkim Lushaj, Vera Malsia, Dodë Doçi, Mercedes Hunt, and Ervin Buçpapaj

Abstract—Tourism and coastal lines are the business sectors since centuries especially in the European Nations and Albania is one such spots. However, in recent decades tourism is experienced as vulnerability of the surrounding ecological conditions of air, soil, water, land and the communities that are dependant and sharing the ecosystem among flora and fauna. Experts opine that apart from the maintenance of near-originality of ecological biodiversity the tourism rather known as ecotourism an indigenous socio-cultural maintenance of indigenous/traditional knowledge of the local people must be well cared in order to sustain on sustainable grounds. As a general tendency, growth of tourism has been affected by the deterioration in the economic conditions on one aspect and unsustainable ecological areas affected since human interventions earlier to this has negative impact on futuristic tourist spots.

However, tourism in Albania as of now is 11% of GDP and coastal regions accounting to 2-4%. An amicable Mediterranean climate with 300 sunny days similar parameters of Greece and Spain throws up sustainable ecotourism in future decades provided public

Arnisa Lushaj is with L'ecole Nationale Superieure d'Architecture de Paris La Vallete (ENSAPLV), 144 Avenue de Flandre 75019, Paris, France (email: arnisa.lushaj@yahoo.com); Arvjen Lushaj is with Dept. of Architecture, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Poytechnic University of Tirana, Albania (email: arvjen.lushaj@gmail.com); Sunitha N. Seenappa is with ECO-BELT R&D Pvt. Ltd., #232, Managanahalli, Hosur Post, Bidadi Hobli, Ramanagara Taluk and District, Karnataka, India (email: drsunithanseenappa@gmail.com); Georgia Butina Watson is with Department of Planning, Faculty of Technology, Design and Environment, Oxford Brookes University, Oxford, UK (email: gbutina@brookes.ac.uk); Bashkim Lushaj is with Institute of Geosciences, Energy, water and Environment, Polytechnic University of Tirana, Albania (email: bmlushaj@hotmail.com); Vera Malsia is with Department of Environmental Protection, Environmental Impact Assessment Centre, Tirana, Albania (email: verasher1963@hotmail.com); Dode Doçi is with Company of "Lura" Ltd., Academy of Construction of Tirana Ltd., Tirana, Albania (email: aldadoci@yahoo.it); Mercedes Hunt is with The International Ecotourism Society, P.O.Box 96503 #34145 Washington, DC 20090 United States (email: mhunt@ecotourism.org) and Ervin Buçpapaj is with Institute of Geosciences, Energy, water and Environment, Polytechnic University of Tirana, Albania (ebucpapaj@gmail.com).

services namely, transportation, road safety, lodging, food availability, recreational regiments, banking accessibility are as per the World Tourism Organizations' protocols. Thus as of Albanian situation, classification of ecotourism activities to safe-guard the localities with its maintenance of ecological land, water and climate has become a paramount importance with a wanting and satisfactory options through harnessing human energy for profit and fitness of ecological flora and fauna. A check on anthropogenic wastes and their safer utilizations inclusive of agricultural and industrial operations in line with Lalzi Bay Coastal Line are of utmost importance for the reason that the Adriatic Sea Coast is the one long stretch of Albanian Lifeline. The present work is based on the methodology of the sustainable management of the same issue.

Keywords—Albania, ecotourism, Lalzi Bay, sustainability.

I. INTRODUCTION

RECENT decades have seen emergent issues that bear potentially massive risks for the long-term trajectory of coastal environments and the uses we make of them. These issues have raised awareness, and in some cases, motivated investment of much funding and research and management efforts in safe-guarding the localities of the coastal belt. On most of the occasions, coastal lines and tourism go hand-in-hand as business in creating huge industrial activities through stakeholder of private sectors, governmental, nongovernmental and NGO based networks that are always prone to vulnerability in terms of dwindling ecology (anthropological stress) caused at the level of climate, soil, water, flora and fauna which limits/shifts the survival of indigenous people of that particular locality. Again from economic growth, the business of tourism has created sensitivity in the sectors of socio-cultural aspects.

Experts opine that apart from the maintenance of near-originality in biodiversity it is of truth that the originality of indigenous socio-cultural maintenance of

indigenous/traditional knowledge of the local people must be well protected in order to sustain uniqueness of the near-originality of the tourist areas. [3] Dabour, (2003), opines that touristic activities generate significant economic benefits to both host countries and tourists' home countries alike. [10] Malsia-Lushaj et al., (2012) have clearly shown the aspects under prompt activities for the sustainable ecotourism activities throughout the coastal zone of Lalzi Bay, Durres County, Albania taking as one example and the methodology benefits to mark other areas of the Mediterranean Regions of Albania fit to put under Biodiversity Reserves through ecotourism.

Growth in the tourism sector has been affected by the deterioration in the economic conditions [3] (Dabour, 2003) on one aspect and on the other due to deterioration of ecological sustainability in the biodiversity regions of the tourist spots. Table I shows region wise tourism earner during 2001, (adapted from the data [3] Dabour, 2003) and summarizing the problems facing tourism and the development of a sustainable tourism sector. [3] Dabour, (2003), enlists the following aspects:

1. Lack of inherent tourism potential based on natural/historical/cultural resources;
2. Lack of knowledge and awareness even fundamental cognizance of the economic importance of tourism and its positive impact as a potential source of foreign exchange and employment;
3. Lack of technical know-how and weak promotional activity as modern industrial perspectives;
4. Lack of tourism related infrastructure like hotels and lodging services; transport and communications; safety and security etc.
5. Lack of tourism investments as service oriented projects to minimize problems.
6. Lack of consistent tourism strategies and policies in the government departments and tourism private agencies.
7. Lack of tourism diversification as establishments of new touristic spots/destinies and developments.
8. Lack of tourism safety either positive/negative perspectives.

Tourism in Albania accounts to 11% of GDP [7] (Jupe and Bundo, web access) and coastal regions accounting to 2-4% of GDP and thus management and implementations of Ecotourism are pre-requisites. Last 2-3 decades, Albania has seen the cause and effect of several decades of uncontrollable exploitations of the coastal regions of tourist importance. Almost all of the emergent issues to be borne as potentially massive risks for the long-term trajectory of Albania's coastal environments namely [10] (Malsia-Lushaj et al, 2012):

- ⇒ Sandy ecological uncertainties at the level of geological, hydrological and soil climate;
- ⇒ Coastal forest range uncertainties with its affected flora and fauna;

- ⇒ Changes in climate due to organic pollution (from agro-industrial refuse, wet/biodegradable garbage, sewage sludge biosolids), automobile pollution and industrial gas/smoke release;
- ⇒ Impairment of soil and water due to run away and/or leachates of chemical fertilizers and pesticides from agricultural activities and release of toxic compounds as effluents/waste waters of organic and/or inorganic nature from the industrial sectors.

Although Albania has taken rapid strides in alternations and mitigation and diverting the due causes based on motivated investments in terms of research and management, yet due to economic constraints, the upliftment of one of its bio-sensitive and bio-vulnerable coastal line - Lalzi Sea Bay currently demands International attention (on monetary grounds) at large apart from local, regional and national work enforcement for safe-guard of economic-socio-cultural areas by the applications and implementations of scientific-technological-engineering knowledge to create caring atmosphere under sustainable biodiversity of Albania's most income generating region.

At this juncture biodiversity and ecotourism as per the guidelines of UN (2003) come in as necessity. Ecotourism is meant as activities of leisure/business/recreation/study/research etc. It is one of the faculties that increase GDP. Albania with its 300 days of a calendar year has sunny days with Mediterranean climate as that of Greece and Spain opens up its avenues for ecotourism. However, public services are pre-requisites like transportation, lodging, food availability, recreation, banking facilities etc., as per the World Tourism Organization's Standard Classification of Tourism Activities but the safe-guard of the localities with its ecological surroundings of land, water and climate has become a wanting and satisfactory options as the per the mentioned details of UN (2006).

The present manuscript is based on the excerpts of the methodology book prepared by [10] Malsia-Lushaj et al., (2012), a concrete example of Lalzi Bay, Durres County, Albania covering the fundamental, natural, and economic and social sciences for estuaries, coasts and marine areas to emphasize the links to integrated and sustainable management of 7 Km of Lalzi Bay stretch. The methodology book is based on the author's undisputed issues in the coastal science and management calls for researchers and environmental manager and policy makers, pedagogues for the explorations and implementations of ecotourism sectors. The methodology book also reveals the issues brought to streamlines since 2001 to 2010 marking the efforts to gain that extra GDP for Albania through ecotourism sectors by undisturbing the indigenous locals but to provide job oriented activities in sustainable way.

II. ECOTOURISM AND BIODIVERSITY

Basic biological sciences and their specialized wings have taken rapid strides not only in research and study but in maintenance of natural resources of all faculties of ecology namely, forests, mangroves, wetlands, streams, marshes, bushes, plains, hills, flora, fauna and microcosm units of soil-water-climate etc through the Law and Order for biodiversity and ecotourism of that particular geo-climatic orientations; shortly, Ecotourism and biodiversity (as two faces of a coin) bring forth Human Rights and Global Responsibility. Table II – enlists the salient features of ecotourism (adapted from Wikipedia).

Wikipedia defines ecotourism as, “a form involving visiting fragile, pristine and relatively undisturbed natural areas, intended as a low-impact and often small scale alternative to standard commercial/mass tourism to educate the traveler, to provide funds for ecological conservation, to directly benefit the economic development and political empowerment of local communities and to foster different cultures of Human Rights”. The term “Ecotourism was coined by [4] Hetzer in 1965 and started ecotourism in early 1970s and later Ceballos-Lascurain popularized it in 1983s (Wikipedia). According to [4] Drumm and Moore (2005), ecotourism can be simply defined as – responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment and improves the well-being of local people.

Ecotourism and Biodiversity march hand-in-hand and the successes that bring are many ultimately creating harmonies with nature for sustainability – a true and sole consoling activity since industrialization times. Harnessing human energy through ecotourism maintains biodiversity of all natural resources of land, water, and climate so much so that ecological systems tend to get balanced keeping check on anthropogenic dwindling activities of agricultural and industrial sectors without hampering the productive systems of agriculture and industry but with much more eco-conscious awareness. The conservation of environment and its wideness as a new industry, through Biodiversity and Ecotourism purposes offer more flexibility on day-to-day basis, under mitigation programs to minimize climate changing, in all contexts and reaching through the utility competitive management methods, towards the integrated and permanent sustainable development, as a better future for all [10] (Malsia-Lushaj et al., 2012).

Ecotourism establishes and sustains on the grounds of near-naturalness of the ecological stability with its originality even though the stretch utilized as tourism spots as revenue generating units. Thus ecotourism is meant as ecologically sustainable tourism. The primary focus of ecotourism is based on the followings:

- Experiences of the still existing natural areas and to foster environmental, cultural understandings;
- Appreciation of the conservation methodologies based on traditional indigenous locals;
- Conservation to its near-naturalness;

- Protective assemblages in lines of land, water and atmosphere;
- Research and development in lines of biodiversity.
- Data records of man-made mistakes and steps to be implantable to revert back;
- Distribution of returns for conservation purposes as well as to regional and local stakeholders.

Ecotourism while still at a relatively modest level of development in a given region shall provide opportunities as well as challenges for the conservation and sustainable wise use of biodiversity along with manmade resources and such actions are brisk since year 2002 – mark of International Year of Ecotourism. Environmentally sustainable investments in the ecotourism sector produce vital benefits to local communities and provide an important and viable alternative investments with positive perspectives not only in lines of business as tourism but also conserves biodiversity. However, the negative and/or positive impacts needs to be watched and reassembled with time and space; can be achieved through the development of new and innovative eco-engineering management systems with a special focal point of ecotourism Vs ecological sustainability based on natural biological spheres that exist in accordance to soil-water-climate. Henceforth, the current team of experts discusses the *modus operandi* for its dual role as economical returns in line with ecological wants for the sustainable benefits of Albanian Nation.

Thus ecotourism has become of paramount figure to uplift socio-economic status of the indigenous areas to retain to its near originality and then further to hasten by means of sustainability. Sustainable development can be traced back to our original old world practices of anthropogenic nature with its soil, waters and atmospheres were that were harnessed and safe-guarded to its near originality without exploitations. [3] Dabour (2003) has detailed out the problems facing tourism in the OIC member countries and suggests policy recommendations to strengthen co-operation in a sustainable way. [11] Martha, (2008), gives seven key principles of ecotourism although the list may be limitless and each factor stresses the important criteria taken to safeguarding of our blue planet:

- ⇒ Traveling to natural destinations;
- ⇒ Impact minimization;
- ⇒ Building environmental awareness;
- ⇒ Providing direct financial benefits for conservation
- ⇒ Providing economic benefits and empowerment for locals;
- ⇒ Respecting local culture; and
- ⇒ Supporting Human Rights and democratic movements.

III. ECOTOURISM CHALLENGES AND CONSTRAINS FACED BY OTHER COUNTRIES

Through the above approaches, multiple sustainable benefits are provided to the biodiversity: as restoration programs of the locality; eco-conscious livelihood among locals; job opportunities for many in all areas; study through all faculties of research and development and implementations; eco-businesses of big and small with individualistic, unique cultural heritage based on bio-geo factors; progressive opportunities to establish co-operative cottage units from raw to finished goods be it food, clothing, consumable items that are indigenous to that particular locality. Table III provides an outlook into the positive/negative aspects of ecotourism (Wikipedia). [8] Lau et al., (2007) has clearly outlined the case study of biodiversity conserve area of Yanayacu pucate watershed/drainage river systems under ecotourism establishments with the support of USAID and other NGOs to operate the systems through local/indigenous people and has shown the constraints faced over the years. A feasibility study [2] (Campana and Flores, 2007), revealed that one of the greatest weakness of the project of Oyacachi Thermal Waters Complex in the part of Cayambe – Coca Reserve was the lack of reinvestment strategy after USAID and that threatened the sustainability of the ecotourism initiative. As current challenges and proposed solutions, [5] Guerrero, (2007), highlights that the challenge was to position the forum of ecotourism in a way that facilitate achieving political, social and financial sustainability with increased participation and commitment on the part of public agencies as the responsive authorities. [1] Calderon-Barrios (2007), through the model of sustainable community development in the multiple uses reserve of the Lake Atitalan Watershed, in Solola, Gautemala, highlights that the benefits of the tourism are not reaching the communities even though the place is the second most visited sites. Due to lack of planning, the ecotourism has developed in an empirical and somewhat piecemeal manner and the main challenge lies in consolidating local tourisms' systems and integrating under Community Tourism Network. In Mexico vast majority of forests are privately owned by indigenous and rural communities of av. 5,000 ha/community [12] (Perdomo and Nieto, 2007). Policies for avoiding deforestation are required and yet to create benefiting the owners of the forests economically survival models are needed thus being the challenge and constraints.

Under the Forestry Incentives Program in Guatemala [12] (Revolorio, 2007), 1% of the country's regular income budget are awarded to landowners including municipalities engaged in reforestation and management of natural forests. The current challenges are to promote the supply of forest products and services and to promote efforts to legalize property titles and to increase private investment industry. In Costa Rica, a decentralized and de-concentrated management model was implemented for the National System of concentrated areas to encourage citizen participation, to control over forests, wildlife and protected wild lands [6] (Jimenez and Suarez,

2007). The current challenges are improving the financial accounting system and political and institutional commitments with legal backing as essential and required rise in awareness programs.

[13] Rodriguez (2007), in his case study of Ecuador, reveals that most of the indigenous groups possess large territories with high biodiversity, capable of producing different environmental services but traditional economies, lack of technical capacity in the indigenous organizations and internal politics make the effective implementations of large-scale environmental service compensation program difficult. And he stress that the community-based tourism can overcome the lacunae. In Mexico [12] (Perdomo and Nieto, 2007), as fresh water conservative initiative, identified the need to rehabilitate the areas of domestic water supply and improve yield to traditional crops, as > 70% of the fresh water being lost through evaporation, infiltration and wasted, so drip tape technology was installed and success were shown; however, the challenges and limitations are funds that to set up Solid Trust Fund to guarantee the long-term sustainability and conservation efforts in the valley has to be considered.

Carbon sequestration at three levels were taken up [15] (Tiepolo, 2007), in Atlantic forests of Brazil as Forest Restoration, Forest Conservation and Watershed Programs on success basis but the challenges and constraints imposed were inclusion of landowner participation (in-kind donors, crucial potential benefactress-stakeholders), funding availability, implementation capacity, conservation of short term to long term goals and securing the support at all levels. Another case study through direct funding for restoration services related to water taken up in Atlantic Forest, Brazil [16] (Veiga, 2007), inclusive of sewage treatment facilities. Even municipality to pay for environmental services; however the current challenges and proposed solutions are to foster scientific studies linking forest cover and water protection (i.e., water yield and regulation) through empirical and modeling experiments and to develop models of contracts for maintenance.

IV. NEED FOR ECOLOGICAL SUSTAINABILITY IN ALBANIA COASTAL LINE THROUGH ECOTOURISM

Concurrently, awareness raising and capacity building systems are being developed and being implemented, to ensure long-term ecological sustainable impacts and effects. One such aspect is the Ecotourism for its dual role for the nation as returns in terms of money and returns in terms of sustainable ecological biodiversity. Methods and methodologies model initiatives and model activities are being ensured but on limited and slow steps against vast ecological destructions already existing [10] (Malsia-Lushaj, 2012). As per the statistics of International tourism, Europe and America (industrialized countries) has tourist-generating and tourist-receiving markets than the developing countries apart from some of the Nations of East Asia, Pacific, South Asia, Africa and Middle East [3] (Dabour, 2003). Ecotourism at Lalzi Bay, Albania has opportunities in many ways as:

- ⇒ As environmental education;
- ⇒ As revenue generation;
- ⇒ As protected area justification;
- ⇒ As employment;
- ⇒ As biodiversity maintenance and improvement
- ⇒ As visitor appreciation and awareness of uniqueness;
- ⇒ As cultural heritage of community based continuity;
- ⇒ As cultural exchange across the globe;
- ⇒ As sustainable and stronger economy.

“Lura” resort is located at the center of the prestigious Lalzi Bay, in the North of Durres, Albania. This area is renowned for its beautiful unspoiled virgin sandy beaches and seclusion and privacy for its Beautiful landscaped grounds, less than thirty minutes from Tirana International Airport; stunning views of the Dajti mountain range from the rear, the resort is perfectly positioned to capitalize on Albania’s fast rising popularity and international prominence. One of the authors, Doçi, from Lura Ltd., with its Lura Resort, established at Lalzi Bay, North of Durres, Albania, is renowned for its still beautiful and unspoiled sandy beaches well known for its seclusion and privacy for the tourists all over the world. The location, Lura Resort with natural and introduced landscaped grounds is a thirty minutes drive from Tirana International Airport; create a time immemorial stunning views of the Dajti Mountain Range makes Lura Resort a perfectly positioned capitalization for Albania.

It seems timely, at a time of economic constraints, and a time when too many issues demand local, regional, national and international attention, to take a hard look at the evidentiary basis, current data, and future predictions surrounding the issues. Ecotourism while still at a relatively modest level of development in the region (Albania) provides opportunities as well as challenges for the conservation and sustainable wise use of biodiversity with its other natural and manmade resources. It is argued that in order to transform research on sustainable ecotourism to a more scientific level, systems perspective and an interdisciplinary approach are indispensable.

V. LALZI BAY AND SUSTAINABLE ECOTOURISM

[11] Martha, (2008), stress that ever since 1980s ecotourism has been felt as critical endeavor by environmentalists and hope to develop untouched human interventions for the future generations. Through a ten year project (2001 to 2010) led by [9] Bashkim Lushaj et al., (2010), has come up with a voluminous methodological document – “Challenges and opportunities for biodiversity conservation and sustainable development of ecotourism in Lalzi Bay, Durres County, Albania: Today’s science for tomorrow’s management”. The team initiated the study and recorded of data of various vulnerable aspects of the entire stretch of coastal region Lalzi Bay and experienced the biodiversity and other natural resources under serious threat from unsustainable exploitation

of land, soil and water by human activities with uncontrollable release of contamination, soil erosion, coastal damage, land-use changes, climatologically changes etc., namely a few.

[4] Drumme and Moore (2005), enlists potential tourism threats which can be well applicable to Lalzi Bay Ecotouristic Industry that can be seen as:

- ⇒ Environmental degradation;
- ⇒ Cultural distortion;
- ⇒ Diminished visitor experience;
- ⇒ Industry instability;
- ⇒ Increased control by outsiders;
- ⇒ Economic distortions and Crowding.

However, the team of [10] Malsia-Lushaj et al., (2012), stress that ecotourism an ecologically sustainable project has a primary focus on experiencing natural areas that fosters environmental and cultural understanding, appreciation and conservation, so it is every Albanian’s dream project and let not wait for someone else to do that even though the country currently undergoing economical crisis, however, appeals through the Government for technological implementations that are sound and cost oriented. The document being itself is a working document, will be used by the project partners as guidance for sustainable development of ecotourism and biodiversity management plans in the entire stretch of Lalzi Bay, Albania.

VI. CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES AT LALZI SEA BAY

According to [10] Malsia-Lushaj et al., (2012), the methodology guide with a concrete example of Lalzi Bay, Durres County, Albania will cover the fundamental natural, economic and social sciences for estuaries, coasts and marine areas and emphasis the links to the integrated and sustainable management of these areas. The outline details of the Lalzi Bay prior to 2001 and later 2010 has been enumerated in the Tables IV – XXX, that highlights the considerations taken up at every important aspects under the following sectors by Doçi (engineer-administrator): (1) Human Resource Management (HRM); (2) Territorial Reform (3) Land inventory frame work; (4) Management of air pollution emissions; (5) Water utilization systems; (6) Soil management program (contamination and erosion); (7) Dwindling fish population and pollution; (8) Management of wild fauna and illegal hunting; (9) Social/mass mobilization and public awareness; (10) Natural forests Vs. Legislation; (11) Management of urban environment and public safety; (12) Waste management plan; (13) A system of environmental accounting and education; (14) Mandatory protocols for pollution abatement; (15) Licenses and permits (Mandatory/operation); (16) Faculty of technical data development; (17) Faculty of product and service policies and strategies; (18) Industrial waste management plan; (19) Traffic management plan; (20) Energy consumption/utility (industrial/urban); (21) Action plan for climate and climate change; (22) Economic upliftment of low-level community; (23) Shelter/housing for the community; (24) Biodiversity

conservation (for socio-cultural benefits); (25) Account of economic value and benefits (biodiversity conservation); (26) Neglected biodiversity conservation; (27) Sporadic management of ecotourism.

Project “Challenges and opportunities for biodiversity conservation and sustainable development of ecotourism in Lalzi Bay, Durres County, Albania” by [10] Malsia-Lushaj et al., (2012) has been developed and it is continuing in the framework. The document being a working document shall be used by the project partners as guidance for the sustainable development of ecotourism and biodiversity management plans in the region of Lalzi Bay Albania compiling serious of case studies based on observations, research and their experiences with the implementation of methodology provided as guide and guidelines. The case studies will provide examples and experiences from the practice of successes and failures of ecotourism and conservation management planning in the region of the Lalzi Bay, Durres County, Albania achieved through development of new and innovative management systems with a special focus on ecotourism-related uses on the sites.

Concurrently, awareness raising and capacity building systems are being developed and implemented, to ensure long-term sustainable impacts and effects. Environmentally sustainable investments in ecotourism sector could produce vital benefits to communities and provide an important and viable alternative to investments with positive biodiversity impacts and effects. Ecotourism model initiatives and activities are being initiated to ensure distribution of returns for conservation purposes as well as to regional and local stakeholders. For a successful sustainable development of Ecotourism, [4] Drumme and Moore (2005), suggests essential elements in a community setting as:

- ⇒ Planning;
- ⇒ Protected natural areas;
- ⇒ Financing;
- ⇒ Sustainable activities;
- ⇒ Education, training and partnerships.

Now the conservation of environment and its wise use for new industry, ecotourism and other purposes are becoming a more flexible on day-to-day basis, under influences of climate changing, under all contexts and performances that are reaching through utility competitive management methods, towards integrated and permanent sustainable development as fulfillment of individual obligation - a major need of present time for better future for all. As analyzed by [9] Bashkim Lushaj et al., (2010), staff of Lura resort company Ltd., (2001), a “problem tree”, at Lalzi Bay has been detailed out impact/s and effect/s of poor conservation, non-restoration and unwise use of Lalzi Bay, poverty of the regional and local community and indigenous people and the lacunae being seen as few/lack of multiple goods and services for the new industry – ecotourism.

The biodiversity and the natural resources are faced with a serious threat due to unsustainable exploitation of

anthropogenic activities on one hand and their repercussion effects of pollution (of land, water and atmosphere), soil damage, soil erosion and landslides on the other has posed not-so-easy irreparable conditions along the entire stretch of Lalzi Bay, Durres County, Albania in terms of cost, time and human expertise. These coastal stretches however are one of the Albanian tourism spots that need to be replenished back to its originality - a challenge taken up by the current team. The case studies have provided, are providing and will provide examples and experiences from the practice about the factors of success and failure of ecotourism and conservation management planning in the region of the Lalzi Bay, Durres County, Albania.

[4] Drumme and Moore, (2005), opine that for a successful, sustainable Ecotourism Industry, an Ecotourism Partnerships are essential commodity as:

- ⇒ Local communities;
- ⇒ Government Agencies;
- ⇒ Non-Governmental Organizations;
- ⇒ Funders;
- ⇒ Ecotourists;
- ⇒ Education Sectors.

VII. CONCLUSION

The growing demand as nature-based tourism otherwise Ecotourism has sparked the interest to address the impacts of the tourism industry [4] (Drumme and Moore, 2005) yet world tourism increased by 74% in 2000 supporting 200 million jobs worldwide [18] (WTO, 2001), yet travelers seek more remote destinations and eco-friendly developments as tourist spots in a way hastening the steady and sustainable ecotourism initiatives as any country’s Global Economy and Albania is making rapid strides in these ‘greener lines for greener pastures’. The success shown by [10] Malsia-Lushaj, 2012 – a renowned book (based on observations, research, development, training and workshops), the authors disputed issues in Coastal Science and Management to bringing in together researchers, environmental managers, policy makers, pedagogues, and graduate students to explore collaborations, challenges and to spark new ideas, with the aim of learning and deciphering about marine/coastal/transitional systems with catches on leading-edge techniques; lastly, appreciating the constraints of the science and the management, in particular for new industry - ecotourism in Lalzi Bay, Durres County, Albania as one of the most renowned ‘green and sustainable tourism of Albania’ as shown in the current paper by the authors.

Fig. 1 Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay, in earlier conditions

Fig. 2 Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay, the present status

TABLE I
 REGION WISE TOURISM EARNER DURING 2001 (DABOUR, 2003)

Region	US \$(billion)
Europe	230.1
Americas	122.4
Pacific/East Asia	82.0
Middle East	11.2
South Asia	4.7

TABLE II

SALIENT FEATURES OF ECOTOURISM (ADAPTED FROM WIKIPEDIA)

Salient features of ecotourism	
1.	A socially responsible travel for environmental sustainability apart from personal growth.
2.	Cultural heritage has given of primary attraction apart from ecological, flora and fauna areas.
3.	A tourist fosters greater appreciation for natural habitats from the biodiversity aspects.
4.	Minimizes the negative aspects of conventional tourism on the environment and will have positive impacts on the cultural integrity of local/indigenous people.
5.	As an integral part of ecotourism, promotion of recycling, energy efficiency and water conservation will be implemented.
6.	Creates economic perspectives of the local/indigenous people.
7.	Creates environmental and social responsibility in the travelers.
8.	Supports Human Right and provides direct financial investments for conservation.
9.	Waste minimization will be ensured and cuts down luxury in the utilizations.
10.	Can actively participate in the management of ecotourism for socio-economic benefits.
11.	As conservationists provide surplus jobs for the localities as indigenous citizens.
12.	Supports small stakeholders to ensure investment for sustainable developments.
13.	Discourages mass tourism and mass constructions in fragile areas of biodiversity.
14.	For Third World Countries help in environmental protection and financial benefits.
15.	Destiny to newer localities can be established.
16.	Ecofriendly mentality will be inculcated.
17.	Ecotourism certification program encourages the youngsters into the fields of ecology.

TABLE III

PROVIDES AN OUTLOOK INTO THE POSITIVE/ NEGATIVE ASPECTS OF ECOTOURISM (WIKIPEDIA)

Improving sustainability	
Regulation and accreditation	Ecologically destructive green washed operations like underwater hotels, helicopter tours, and wildlife theme parks can be categorized as ecotourism along with canoeing, camping, photography, and wildlife observation. The failure to acknowledge responsible, low-impact ecotourism puts legitimate ecotourism companies at a competitive disadvantage.
Guidelines and education	An environmental protection for cause-and-effect will be implemented for awareness on environmental issues, and care about the places via Tour Guides.
Small scale, slow growth and local control	The lack of sustainability highlights the need for small scale, slow growth, and locally based ecotourism. Local peoples have a vested interest in the well being of their community, and are therefore more accountable to environmental protection than multinational corporations. The lack of control, westernization, adverse impacts to the environment, loss of culture and traditions outweigh the benefits of establishing large scale ecotourism.
Natural resource management	
1.	Can be utilized as specialized tools for the development of ecotourism.
2.	Abundance of biodiversity areas can be established and managed.
3.	Several plans and opportunities can be introduced and to maintain untouched habitats.
4.	Effective sustainability planning, maximum social and economic

benefits for local communities can be provided.	
5. Minimum negative impacts on cultural heritage and minimum negative impacts on the environment can be done.	
Criticism	
Negative impact of tourism	At the local level, ecotourism has become a source of conflict over control of land, resources, and tourism profits.
Direct environmental impacts	The environment suffers because local communities are unable to meet the infrastructure demands of ecotourism and have to part with their drinking water systems.
Local people	Foreign investors may not support local people and may displace them.
Threats to indigenous cultures	Pushing people onto marginal lands with harsh climates, poor soils, lack of water, and infested with livestock and disease. May do little to enhance their livelihoods even when a proportion of ecotourism profits are directed back into the community.
Mismanagement	The <u>tragedy of the commons</u> offers another model for economic unsustainability from environmental protection, in ecotourism sites utilized by many companies.

TABLE IV
HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT (HRM)

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No management plan; 2. Lack of work force; 3. Care for employees lacked, resulting in irresponsibility, and lack of training and/or attractive job selections; 4. No ensuring compliance with employment and labor laws; 5. Overseeing organizational leadership and culture; 6. Lack of Legal Authorization; 7. Labor Union Scenario with poor physical health and poor mental abilities; 8. Company's primary liaison was not the credentials; 9. No educational schemes or plans; 10. Lack of interest of ruling parties in the biodiversity conservations (of wetland, lake, fauna and flora); 11. Without policies and strategies for ecotourism; 12. No mandatory rules and regulations for coastal border policy; 13. Lack of educative programs, namely: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of educative facilities; • Lack of consultancy services; • Without Law enforcement; • Unsustainable individual ranching practices; • Lack of trained staff. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. HRM plan has been created and implemented; 2. Management of an organization's workforce created and implemented with selection, training and rewarding of employees; 3. Ensured compliance with labor laws; 4. HRM serves as the company's primary liaison with the employees' representatives (usually a labor union); 5. Educational plans/schemes for human beings resources management implemented with health services at Lalzi Bay; 6. Successful programs of education, consultation and information with monitored HRM; 7. Sustainable and individual ranching practices for HRM; 8. Monitoring and audit of HR with guideline/standards; 9. Effective control; 10. Changes in policies and strategies with trained

staff.

TABLE V
TERRITORIAL REFORM

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No assessment criteria for the a long-term and balanced development of the county territory is ensured; 2. No assessment criteria for the infrastructure required for the performance of the tasks of a county local government exists; 3. No assessment criteria for the size of the county territory; 4. No assessment criteria for the number of permanent residents of the county territory; 5. No assessment criteria for the density of permanent residents in the county territory; 6. No assessment criteria for the accessibility of the services provided by the county local government; 7. No assessment criteria for the economic, geographical and historical unity of the territorial local governments comprising the county; and 8. No assessment criteria for the optimum establishment of the territory of the county local government have been ensured, taking into account the interests of the neighboring county local governments. 9. Lack of educative programs, namely: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of educative facilities; • Lack of consultancy services; • Without Law enforcement; • Unsustainable individual ranching practices; • Lack of trained staff. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assessment criteria will be taken into account for the a long-term and balanced development of the county territory is ensured; 2. Assessment criteria will be taken into account for the infrastructure required for the performance of the tasks of a county local government exists; 3. Assessment criteria will be taken into account for the size of the county territory; 4. Assessment criteria will be taken into account for the number of permanent residents of the county territory; 5. Assessment criteria will be taken into account for the density of permanent residents in the county territory; 6. Assessment criteria will be taken into account for the accessibility of the services provided by the county local government; 7. The economic, geographical and historical unity of the territorial local governments comprising the county; and 8. Assessment criteria will be taken into account for optimum establishment of the territory of the county local government has been ensured, taking into account the interests of the neighboring county local governments. 9. Educational plans/schemes for human beings resources management implemented with health services at Lalzi Bay; 10. Successful programs of education, consultation and

	<p>information for the Territorial Reform;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 11. Sustainable and individual ranching practices for Territorial Reform; 12. Monitoring and audit of Territorial Reform will be with guideline/standards; 13. Effective control; 14. Changes in policies and strategies with trained staff. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. individual ranching practices for Air quality; 9. No stipulated standards for effective control; 10. Lack of inputs for new approaches; 11. Old policies and strategies; 12. Lack of trained staff; 13. Does not comply the European Emission Standards. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Effective low enforcement for air quality; 7. Monitoring and audit of air pollution in place; 8. Sustainable and individual ranching practices for air quality; 9. Effective control measurement; 10. Staff trained; 11. Changes in policies and strategies; 12. Air quality under the European emission standards.
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TABLE VI
LAND INVENTORY FRAMEWORK

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of land use inventory management plan; 2. Lack of set up of land use inventory system; 3. Land conversions into artificial areas resulting in significant deforestations; 4. Consumption of arable land into urban developmental areas on one side and on the other angle shift in crop patterns into orchards and vineyards; 5. Some percent of total land taken for urban settlements; 6. Lack of educative programs for land utilization act; 7. Lack of information centers and lack of consultations; 8. Lack of effective control measures what so ever; 9. Lack of trained staff; 10. Lack of improvements in policies and strategies. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. As framework for environmental accounting; 2. An application is under process; 3. Land use inventory management planned and is implementing; 4. Set up a land use inventory system; 5. However so far no education program for land use inventory management plan is in place; 6. No information and consultation processes; 7. No effective law enforcement; 8. No monitoring for land use inventory management plan in place; 9. No effective control; 10. No new mentality or no new approach to problems; 11. No trained staff; 12. No changes in policies and strategies.

TABLE VII
MANAGEMENT OF AIR POLLUTION EMISSIONS

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Release of Air emissions; 2. Impure Air quality in the atmosphere; 3. Lack of legislation for Air quality; 4. Lack of implementable approaches; 5. No educative program for Air quality; 6. Lack of guidelines and consultations; 7. No sustainable and 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Air pollution under control; 2. Minimizing and reduction of emissions in the air; 3. Legislation for air pollution adequate and implemented. 4. Education programme for air pollution in place; 5. Successful information and consultation process implemented;

TABLE VIII

WATER UTILIZATION SYSTEMS

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of planning, developing, distribution and management of the optimum use of water resources and water bodies; 2. Poor water management planning against high demand and lack of supply management based on equitable satisfaction of water demands; 3. No norms fixed for the release of polluted water. Aquatic destructions recordable in the shallow marine waters, estuarine/Delta Rivers of Ishem, Erzeni and Tarini torrent; 4. Same destructive trends recordable in the salt and brackish marshes as well as coastal brackish lagoons; 5. Deposition of chemical components into the receiving water bodies; 6. Decrease/impairment of aquatic flora, fauna, vegetations; 7. Improper drainage pattern; 8. Incapability's of the ruling parties posing irresolvable conservation of the biosphere reserves of all category; 9. Lack of Legislation for polluted water and lack of technologies for zero discharge; 10. Unchangeable policies and law enforcement. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Planning, developing, distributing and managing the optimum use of water resources. 2. Water management planning to all the competing demands for water and seeks to allocate water on an equitable basis to satisfy all uses and demands; 3. Water resources managed by minimizing of discharges in the water; water resources (shallow marine waters, estuarine (delta) rivers of Ishmi, Erzen and Tarini torrent; 4. Salt and brackish marshes and coastal brackish lagoons destruction and damage identified and enlisted; 5. Drainage pattern surveyed, controlling water expansion; 6. Implementation of water pollution act. There is still inadequate legislation for water pollution and improving watershed water quality; 7. Changes in policies and strategies. Educative program for water quality is in place; 8. Successful information and consultation process are implemented; 9. Effective law enforcement for water quality ensured.

TABLE IX

SOIL MANAGEMENT PROGRAM (CONTAMINATION AND EROSION)

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Poor maintenance of soil. Contamination typical of pesticides, oil leakage and fuel discharges from the dumping sites, landfill leachate, and direct discharge of industrial wastes on the soil; Measurable levels of chemical compounds (hydrocarbons, solvents, heavy metals); Sold wastes (construction debris, garbage) disposal sites directly on the soils; Soil erosion due to run off (from heavy downpour); Soil erosion or landslides due to slope gradient and length a cause for lack of vegetative cover; Soil erosion due to overgrazing and deforestation; Irresponsibility and lack of knowledge of the ruling government in soil conservation programs; Lack of educative programs and untrained staffs; No effective Law enforcement on soil quality; Lack of soil maintenance strategies and policies due to the Lack of interest in the politicians. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Maintenance of soil quality with check on soil erosion; Maintenance o local topography, soil stability, minimized chemical emissions and deposits on soil; 4. Waste disposal under control. Sterilization of mineral recourses; No raw materials and chemicals let on to soil seepage; Minimized and control over construction waste; Check on petrochemical pollution from transport and fuel; Changes in policies and strategies; Education program for soil quality in place; Successful information and consultation process implemented; Effective law enforcement; monitoring for soil quality in place; Sustainable and individual ranching practices for soil quality and effective control on maintenance of soil quality; Staff trained.

TABLE X

DWINDLING FISH POPULATION AND POLLUTION

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Decrease in fish population blamable for over fishing and decreased populations; Replacement of native species by the invasive species; Lack of fish processing industries or units; Illegal trade of fish; Over use of fish as consumable item; Inadequate legalization for fisheries; Lack of knowledge to implement policies and strategies; No educative program for fisheries; Poor or no information centers and consultations provided; No sustainable and individual ranching practices; Change in attitude and change in policies for protective 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Good legislation for fishing in place; Pollution under control; No over fishing and banned explosives; An inventory finalized; 6. Economic incentives for sustainable fishing; A biotic native community of fish growing; 10 % increase in the number of fish; Educational plans/schemes for Lalzi Bay's fish in place; Changes in policies and strategies; Education programme for sustainable fishing in place; Successful information and consultation process implemented; Effective low enforcement for sustainable fishing;

measures are not created as awareness programs.

- Monitoring of fishing in place;
- Effective control;
- Staff trained.

TABLE XI

MANAGEMENT OF WILD FAUNA AND ILLEGAL HUNTING

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Decreasing number of wild fauna and illegal hunting; No preservation of wildlife habitat; Illegal unsustainable and unregulated hunting by local, regional and foreigner communities; Pollution of air, water and soil limits the number of wild fauna; Invasive species replacing native species; Illegal trading of wild fauna especially consumable kinds of animals and birds; Inadequate and old legislation for preservation of the wild fauna and sustainable haunting; No changes in policies and strategies. No effective control, no trained staff, no new mentality of wild life conservation portfolios; Non-sustainable and individual ranching for preservation of the wild fauna and sustainable hunting; No information and no guidelines for protective act. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> A wildlife habitat conserved with good legislation for the wild fauna and hunting areas; Hunting under control; Pollution under control; No illegal and irregular hunting; An inventory finalized; Economic incentives for sustainable the wild fauna and hunting; A biotic native community of wild fauna growing; 15 % increase in the number of the wild fauna (animals and wild fowls); Changes in policies and strategies to the best policy; Educational plans/schemes for Lalzi Bay's wild fauna and hunting in place; Sustainability of all sorts ensured; Education programme for sustainable the wild fauna (animals and wild fowls) and hunting; Successful information and consultation process implemented; Effective low enforcement for sustainable the wild fauna and hunting.

TABLE XII

SOCIAL/MASS MOBILIZATION AND PUBLIC AWARENESS

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> No social mobilization; Low public awareness; Regional people, local community and indigenouse people lack expertise, knowledge and interest in ecotourism policies and implementations; Unimplemented Conservations of Arhus, Ramsar and Espoo; No educational plans/schemes for 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> New farmers, landowners and businesspersons enrolled; Farming community organization and network with relevant government organizations formed; Exchange of cultures with better trained staff and level of community

<p>conservation and its wise use;</p> <p>6. No common understanding regarding protected areas of land and water;</p> <p>7. Very little progress in raising awareness among regional and local community stakeholders (regional and local community and indigenous people and sectoral interests of both in situ and ex situ);</p> <p>8. Lack of public participation in decision-making, and no public participation in study and management as projects;</p> <p>9. No common understanding in terms of conservation and its wise use;</p> <p>10. No accessible justice in environmental matters; and</p> <p>11. No trained staff.</p>	<p>involvement increasing;</p> <p>4. Public participation in Lalzi Bay study and management promoted with a common, shared understanding in Lalzi Bay of its conservation and wise use with ensured positive public awareness;</p> <p>5. A successful information and consultation process implemented;</p> <p>6. Positive changes in policies and strategies with ruling parties aware of the importance of biosphere reserves and conservation of all and for the sustainable development of ecotourism.</p> <p>7. Implementations of Århus, Ramsar and Espoo Convention;</p> <p>8. Change in social-economic structure by direct impacts, such as: new employment, new technology, rising income and population structure;</p> <p>9. Social impact assessment of Lalzi Bay implemented;</p> <p>10. Educational plans/schemes for Lalzi Bay conservation done;</p> <p>11. Trained staff;</p> <p>12. Individual consciousness and oneness established.</p>	<p>Lalzi Bay;</p> <p>6. Lack of adequate legal and institutional regimes;</p> <p>7. Lack of existing biosphere reserve management and lack of protected area management plan;</p> <p>8. Incidences of overgrazing, fire incidences, pollution, illegal logging are still common;</p> <p>9. Protection status is not appropriate and consequently has never been implemented;</p> <p>10. Lack of implementable measurements in the agricultural practices;</p> <p>11. Poor conservation of Lalzi Bay landscape and seascape;</p> <p>12. No restoration programs of meandering streams;</p> <p>13. No flood control measurements and high erosion impact.</p>	<p>woodland conserved;</p> <p>7. 10% increase in number of animals;</p> <p>8. Fire incidence under control;</p> <p>9. Agricultural land protection law implemented;</p> <p>10. Indigenous agro-practices imposed;</p> <p>11. Check on pesticide and grazing;</p> <p>12. No wasteland;</p> <p>13. Increase in livestock breeding;</p> <p>14. Terrestrial and aquatic plants/fauna improved and conserved;</p> <p>15. Driftage and driftwoods cleaned, no noise, solid waste disposal prohibition enacted with proper processes;</p> <p>16. Legislation for wetland conservation and its wise use in place;</p> <p>17. Environmental impact assessment of Lalzi Bay implemented;</p> <p>18. Lalzi Bay landscape conserved;</p> <p>19. Seascape conserved;</p> <p>20. Sedge and reed restored;</p> <p>21. Sediment inflow under control with retention ponds.</p>
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TABLE XIII
NATURAL FORESTS VS. LEGISLATION

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<p>1. Destruction and damage of shrubs, coppice forests, high forests, agricultural lands, pastures;</p> <p>2. Decreasing flora, vegetation, fauna and small and big wildlife;</p> <p>3. Lack of controlling measures in felling of trees;</p> <p>4. Missing Legislation for biosphere reserve, the inadequacy of legislation of protected areas and for protection of marine environment from pollution hazards and destruction and irreparable damage;</p> <p>5. No restoration programs at</p>	<p>1. Good legislation for ecotourism in biosphere reserve or protected area, wetland, lake etc. in place;</p> <p>2. Sustainability in ecotourism;</p> <p>3. All inventories finalized. Indigenous forests, coppices and shrubs safe-guarded, planted, restored and protected;</p> <p>4. Hunting under control;</p> <p>5. Forest function in water retention improved and erosion under control by planting;</p> <p>6. Wildlife habitat and</p>

TABLE XIV
MANAGEMENT OF URBAN ENVIRONMENT AND PUBLIC SAFETY

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<p>1. Noticeable change in population development, and their consequential environmental effects inclusive o public health and safety measures;</p> <p>2. No demographic profile plan and uncontrollable migration in the local as well as regional areas;</p> <p>3. No sense and spatial pattern of metropolitan growth;</p> <p>4. Poor public health and services;</p> <p>5. No changes in policies and strategies.</p> <p>6. No education program for demographic management;</p> <p>7. No effective law enforcement in individual practices for the demographic management;</p> <p>8. No trained staff;</p> <p>9. No effective control;</p> <p>10. No new mentality;</p> <p>11. No new approachability to the problems;</p>	<p>1. Change in population arising from the development, and consequential environmental effects, including urban environment, public health and safety managed by regional and local government;</p> <p>2. Demographic management plan created and implemented;</p> <p>3. Migration under control;</p> <p>4. Studies on natural increase;</p> <p>5. Studies on age and sex structure created and implemented;</p> <p>6. Trained staff implemented;</p> <p>7. Studies on the spatial pattern of metropolitan growth created and implemented;</p> <p>8. Changes in policies and</p>

12. No changes in the policies and law.	strategies etc.; Education program for demographic management in place;
	9. Successful information and consultation process implemented;
	10. Effective law enforcement;
	11. Monitoring for the demographic management in place;
	12. Sustainable and individual practices for the demographic management implemented;
	13. Effective control.

	implemented; 14. Effective control; 15. Staff trained etc.
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TABLE XVI
A SYSTEM OF ENVIRONMENTAL ACCOUNTING AND EDUCATION

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
1. No environmental accounting plan and no implementation;	1. Target period planned and implemented;
2. Target period not implemented.	2. Scope of calculations planned and implemented;
3. No scope for such aspects;	3. Environmental conservation cost and standards for measuring environmental conservation cost planned and implemented;
4. Not planned for environmental conservation and standards for measuring environmental conservation cost;	4. Environmental conservation benefit and standards for measuring environmental conservation benefit planned and implemented;
5. Ruling government fail to understand fail to impose;	5. Items and standards for measuring the economic benefit associated with environmental conservation activities planned and implemented;
6. No educative programs and consultations;	6. Changes in policies and strategies etc.;
7. No effective control and no new mentality;	7. Education programs for environmental accounting in place;
8. No trained staff;	8. Successful information and consultation process implemented;
9. No effective law enforcement;	9. Effective law enforcement;
10. No items and standards for measuring the economic benefit associated with environmental conservation activities unplanned and unimplemented;	10. Monitoring for environmental accounting in place;
11. Environmental conservation cost and standards for measuring environmental conservation cost unplanned and unimplemented.	11. Effective control; 12. Staff trained etc.;
	13. Managing of pollution, contamination, damages etc. by monitoring, audits and controls planned and implemented;
	14. Education program for managing of pollution, contamination, damages etc. by monitoring, audits and controls in place;
	15. Successful information and consultation process;
	16. Effective law enforcement with monitoring done.

TABLE XV
WASTE MANAGEMENT PLAN

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
1. No waste management plan;	1. Waste management implemented;
2. No concept for implementation of integrated solid waste management plan;	2. Plan created and implemented;
3. No waste management plan and on new strategy to engage rural community or trained urban as job initiatives;	3. A good concept for implementation of Integrated Waste Management;
4. Both human wastes and animal wastes need management;	4. New waste strategy that engage the total community;
5. No improvements in hygiene levels.	5. Successful waste and recycling systems set up and dependent on relationships and partnerships;
6. No advancement in science and technology in relation to waste.	6. Human and animal activities generate different kinds of wastes, as domestic, commercial, industrial, municipal, and agricultural wastes under control;
7. Pollution and global warming awareness is lacking;	7. Successful information and consultation process implemented; hygiene levels under control;
8. No education program for SWM.	8. Advancement in science and technology in relation to waste;
9. No trained staff;	9. Monitoring of pollution and global warming, pollution and global warming under control;
10. No changes in policies and strategies.	10. Changes in policies and strategies etc.;
11. Waste monitoring strategies are neglected;	11. Education program for solid waste management in place;
12. Lack of new mentality and concepts among people.	12. Effective law enforcement;
	13. Monitoring for waste management in place; sustainable and individual practices for the waste management

TABLE XVII
MANDATORY PROTOCOLS FOR POLLUTION ABATEMENT

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
1. No stipulated Norms for pollution of contamination, damage and erosion etc.;	1. Target period planned and implemented;
2. No audits and no	2. Scope of calculations planned and implemented;

<p>controls; 3. No implementation and inadequate legislation for managing of pollution contamination; 4. No education program for managing of pollution; 5. No effective law enforcement; 6. Non-sustainable and individual ranching practices for managing of pollution by monitoring, audits and controls; 7. No effective monitoring, for new approaches and new problems; 8. No trained staff; 9. No changes in policies and strategies.</p>	<p>Environmental conservation cost and standards for measuring environmental conservation cost planned and implemented; 3. Environmental conservation benefit and standards for measuring environmental conservation benefit planned and implemented; 4. Items and standards for measuring the economic benefit associated with environmental conservation activities planned and implemented; 5. Changes in policies and strategies; etc. 6. Education programs for environmental accounting in place; 7. Successful information and consultation process implemented; 8. Effective law enforcement; monitoring for environmental accounting in place; 9. Effective control; 10. Staff trained etc.; 11. Managing of pollution, contamination, damages etc. by monitoring, audits and controls planned and implemented; 12. Education program for managing of pollution, contamination, damages etc. by monitoring, audits and controls in place; 13. Successful information and consultation process; 14. Effective law enforcement; 15. Monitoring for all pollutants, contaminations etc. in place.</p>	<p>carrying activities out etc. in place; 4. Non-sustainable and individual ranching practices for operational licenses and permits needed for carrying activities out; 5. No operational licenses and permits needed to carry out activities as guidelines and standards; 6. No new mentality or no new approach to problems; 7. No trained staff; 8. No changes in policies and strategies.</p>	<p>3. Implementation and inadequate legislation for operational licenses and permits needed for carrying activities out; 4. Changes in policies and strategies etc.; 5. Education program operational licenses and permits needed for carrying activities out in place; 6. Successful information and consultation process; 7. Effective law enforcement; monitoring for operational licenses and permits needed for carrying activities out etc. in place; 8. Sustainable and individual ranching practices for operational licenses and permits needed for carrying activities out implemented; 9. Operational licenses and permits needed for carrying activities out guideline values and standards planned and implemented; 10. Effective operational licenses and permits needed for carrying activities out approved and implemented; 11. Staff trained etc.</p>
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TABLE XIX
FACULTY OF TECHNICAL DATA DEVELOPMENT

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<p>1. Sporadic and low level of the technological development; 2. Old and oldest technological development; no changes in policies and strategies; 3. No education program for technological development in place; 4. No information and consultation process; 5. No effective law enforcement; 6. No monitoring for technological development in place; 7. Non-sustainable and individual practices for technological development; 8. No effective control and no trained staff; 9. No changes in policies and strategies; 10. Missing or poor investments for technological development; 11. No new mentality or no</p>	<p>1. Normal level of the technological development in place; 2. Sustainable technological development; 3. Natural increase; 4. Age and sex structure; 5. The spatial pattern of metropolitan growth; 6. Changes in policies and strategies etc.; 7. Education program for technological development in place; 8. Successful information and consultation process; 9. Effective law enforcement; 10. Full investments for technological development; 11. Monitoring for technological development in place; 12. Sustainable and individual practices for technological development; 13. Effective control; 14. Staff trained etc.</p>

TABLE XVIII
LICENSES' AND PERMITS (MANDATORY/OPERATION)

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<p>1. No education program for operational licenses and permits to carry out activities and no effective law enforcement; 2. No information and consultation process; 3. No monitoring for operational licenses and permits needed for</p>	<p>1. Quasi all activities with operational licenses and permits needed for carrying activities out approved by central, regional and/or local governments. 2. Quasi all activities with operational licenses and permits approved and implemented and/or implementing in place;</p>

new approach to problems.	
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TABLE XX

FACULTY OF PRODUCT AND SERVICE POLICIES AND STRATEGIES

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No good developing and adoption of the product and services policies and strategies; 2. With poor mentality policies and strategies; 3. Politicians and local communities unaware of the importance; 4. Lack of sustainable development and changes as and when felt mandatory especially in the biosphere reserve or protected area; 5. No education program for developing and adoption of the product and services policies and strategies in place; 6. No information and consultation process and no effective law enforcement and no sustainable individual practices; 7. No effective control; 8. No new mentality or new approach to problems; 9. No trained staff; 10. No changes in policies and strategies. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Education program for developing and adoption of the product and services policies and strategies in place; 2. Successful information and consultation process; 3. Effective law enforcement; 4. Monitoring for developing and adoption of the product and services policies and strategies in place; 5. Sustainable and individual practices for developing and adoption of the product and services policies and strategies; 6. Effective control; 7. New mentality or new approach to problems; 8. Staff trained; 9. Changes in policies and strategies etc.; 10. A good developing and adoption of the product and services policies and strategies; 11. Positive and change mentality in policies and strategies; 12. Politicians and local communities unaware of the importance of developing and adoption of the product and services policies and strategies; 13. A sustainable developing and adoption of the product and services policies and strategies; 14. Changes in policies and strategies etc.

TABLE XXI

INDUSTRIAL WASTE MANAGEMENT

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No or poor industrial waste management plan; 2. No new waste strategy that should engage the total community; 3. No trained staff; 4. No successful industrial waste and recycling systems that can be dependent on 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Industrial waste management plan implemented. Industrial Waste Management Plan created and implemented; 2. A good concept for implementation of Industrial Integrated Waste Management; 3. New industrial waste strategy

<p>relationships and partnerships;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Industrial activities generate different kinds of industrial wastes and no information and consultation process; 6. Increase in hygiene levels not implemented; 7. Lack of advanced science and technology; 8. No education program for industrial waste management; 9. Lack of effective law enforcement; 10. Non-sustainable and individual practices for the industrial waste management. 	<p>that engage the total community;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Successful waste and recycling systems set up and dependent on relationships and partnerships; 5. Industrial activities generate different kinds of wastes, that are under control; 6. Successful information and consultation process implemented; 7. Hygiene levels under control; 8. Advancement in science and technology in relation to industrial waste; 9. Monitoring of industrial pollution and global warming, industrial pollution and global warming under control; 10. Changes in policies and strategies etc.; 11. Education program for solid waste management in place; 12. Effective law enforcement; 13. Monitoring for waste management in place; 14. Sustainable and individual practices for the waste management implemented; 15. Effective control; 16. Staff trained etc.
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TABLE XXII

TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT PLAN

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Poor traffic management and lacks driving strategies; 2. Limit of persons per vehicle not followed and misuse of public transportation with higher levels of noise pollution; 3. Poorly designed/planned cities that require commuting; 4. Emissions no under control and no changes in policies and strategies as and when required; 5. No new mentality and no new approach to the problems; 6. No education program for traffic management in place; 7. No information and consultation process; 8. No effective law enforcement; 9. No monitoring for traffic management in place; 10. Non-sustainable and 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Vehicle pollution under control; 2. No old or oldest vehicles using too many people; 3. People wanting vehicles with normal seats as they require; 4. Maintained vehicles; 5. Good driving habits; 6. Normal periodic motor vehicle inspection; 7. Emissions under control; 8. Normal level of motor vehicle emissions etc.; 9. Education program for vehicle pollution control in place; 10. Successful information and consultation process; 11. Effective law enforcement; 12. Monitoring vehicle pollution control in place; 13. Sustainable and individual practices for vehicle pollution control; 14. Effective control; 15. Staff trained etc.

individual practices for traffic management and overall no effective control.	
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6. No effective law enforcement; 7. No monitoring climate change in place; 8. Non-sustainable and individual practices for climate change control; 9. No effective control.	5. Effective law enforcement; 6. Monitoring for climate change in place; Sustainable and individual practices for climate change control; 7. Effective control etc.
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TABLE XXIII
ENERGY CONSUMPTION/UTILITY (INDUSTRIAL/URBAN)

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
1. Low production and bad actions in consumption of energy by local and regional communities; 2. Unwise use by public of production and consumption of energy; 3. Use of high lights, noises, vibrations from all activities; 4. Poorly designed cities that require commuting. 5. Production and consumption of energy no under control; 6. No changes in policies and strategies; no new mentality or no new approach to problems; 7. No education program for production and bad consumption of energy in place; 8. No consultations and no effective law enforcement. 9. No monitoring for production and bad consumption of energy in place; 10. Non-sustainable and individual practices for production and bad consumption of energy.	1. Normal production and good consumption of energy. 2. Wise use by public of production and consumption of energy; 3. Good designed cities that require commuting; 4. Production and consumption of energy under control; 5. Changes in policies and strategies; 6. New mentality or new approach to problems etc.; 7. Education program for production and bad consumption of energy in place; 8. Successful information and consultation process; 9. Effective law enforcement; 10. Monitoring for production and bad consumption of energy in place; 11. Sustainable and individual practices for production and bad consumption of energy; 12. Effective control; 13. Staff trained etc.

TABLE XXIV
ACTION PLAN FOR CLIMATE AND CLIMATE CHANGE

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
1. No any action plan for adaptation so far; 2. Emissions by anthropogenic activities and natural phenomena of greenhouse gases affect the heat balance of the Earth, and Lalzi Bay too with the resulting changes in precipitation patterns, rising sea temperatures, extremes and society levels affect how develops; 3. Not yet actions plan with adjustments; 4. No education program for climate change and adoption in place; 5. No or poor information and consultation process.	1. Climate change and adaptation implemented; Emissions by anthropogenic activities and natural phenomena of greenhouse gases affect the heat balance of the Earth, and Lalzi Bay too with the resulting changes in precipitation patterns, rising sea temperatures, extremes and society levels affect how develops under adoption; 2. An action plan with adjustments to them; 3. Education program for climate change and adoption in place; 4. Successful information and consultation process;

TABLE XXV
ECONOMIC UPLIFTMENT OF LOW-LEVEL COMMUNITY

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
1. Low basic and services employment; 2. Labor supply and demand are in contrast between them; 3. Negative local and non local trend for economic base-direct; 4. No education program and poor information strategies; 5. No effective law enforcement; 6. No monitoring on economic base-direct in place; 7. Non-sustainable and individual practices for economic base-direct control; 8. No effective control and low non-basic service provider; 9. No education program for economic base-indirect in place; 10. No or poor information and consultation process; 11. No effective law enforcement; 12. No monitoring on economic base-indirect in place; 13. Non-sustainable and individual practices for economic base-indirect control.	1. Low level of the economic base-indirect of Lalzi Bay community; 2. A good basic and services employment; 3. Labor supply and demand are in good ration between them; 4. Positive local and non local trend for economic base-direct. 5. Education program for economic base-direct in place; 6. A good information and consultation process; effective law enforcement; 7. Monitoring on economic base-direct in place; sustainable and individual practices for economic base-direct control; 8. Effective control; etc. 9. Level in growing in economic base-indirect of Lalzi Bay community; 10. Growing of the non-basic and services employment; 11. Labor supply and demand are in good ratio between them; 12. Positive local and non local trend for economic base-indirect; 13. Education program for economic base-indirect in place; 14. A good information and consultation process; effective law enforcement; 15. Monitoring on economic base-indirect in place; Sustainable and individual practices for economic base-indirect control; 16. Effective control etc.

TABLE XXVI
SHELTER/HOUSING FOR THE COMMUNITY

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
1. Low level in growing of the housing for community; 2. Labor supply and demand is in contrast between	1. A good level in growing of the housing for Lalzi Bay community; 2. Growing of the housing for the Lalzi Bay community;

<p>them;</p> <p>3. Negative local and non local trend for housing for the community;</p> <p>4. No information and consultation process;</p> <p>5. No effective law enforcement;</p> <p>6. No monitoring for housing for the community in place;</p> <p>7. Non-sustainable and individual practices for housing for the community;</p> <p>8. No effective control.</p>	<p>3. Labor supply and demand are in good ratio between them;</p> <p>4. Positive local and non local trend for housing for the Lalzi Bay community;</p> <p>5. Education program for housing for the Lalzi Bay community in place;</p> <p>6. A good information and consultation process; Effective law enforcement;</p> <p>7. Monitoring for housing for the Lalzi Bay community in place;</p> <p>8. Sustainable and individual practices for housing for the Lalzi Bay community;</p> <p>9. Effective control etc.</p>
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<p>utilization of traditional cultural knowledge and values in place;</p> <p>8. No information and consultation process;</p> <p>9. Effective law enforcement; monitoring for the traditional social-cultural values in place;</p> <p>10. Effective control etc.</p>

TABLE XXVIII
ACCOUNT OF ECONOMIC VALUE AND BENEFITS (BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION)

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<p>1. Not taken into account of any sort. The value of economic sustainable development of ecotourism not yet realized;</p> <p>2. Poverty poses the financial mechanism to increase the income of some of the biosphere reserve, protected area, wetland, lake, etc.;</p> <p>3. Money generation through taxes, incentives, tourism income, donors, etc by use of utility competitive management methods not done;</p> <p>4. The lack of financial resources for effective administration;</p> <p>5. Lack of multiple goods and services of high economic values;</p> <p>6. No knowledge of the economic impacts of biosphere reserve, protected area, lake and wetland conservation and its wise use;</p> <p>7. No economical impact assessment. Low level employment at Lalzi Bay and revitalization programs not done for locals;</p> <p>8. Lacks labor market characteristics; Unsustainable economic development makes local and nonlocal trends increasing;</p> <p>9. Persistence in labor unemployment. No strategies;</p> <p>10. Low human development index.</p>	<p>1. Rationality on developing of the financial mechanism to increase income of biosphere reserve;</p> <p>2. Wise use of economical knowledge for the biosphere reserve or protected area, wetland, lake etc.;</p> <p>3. New alternative income generation for farmers, landowners and businessmen. new opportunities for jobs;</p> <p>4. Provision of multiple goods and services of high economic values; conservation and its wise use;</p> <p>5. Grow the income to support future sustainable ecotourism; medium human development index (human development index increasing by 2-3 times more the before); a livelihood impact assessment of Lalzi Bay implemented;</p> <p>6. Change in regional and local living conditions by indirect impact, such as: inflation, new opportunities, health change, etc.;</p> <p>7. Promotion of the coalition and revitalization of the regional and local community; economic impact assessment of Lalzi Bay implemented;</p> <p>8. Educational plans/schemes for Lalzi Bay's economy in place.</p>

TABLE XXIX
NEGLECTED BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
1. Old and no changes in	1. A good conservation of

TABLE XXVII
BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION (FOR SOCIO-CULTURAL BENEFITS)

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<p>1. Lacks wise use for effective utility competitive management of site and at the same time not taken into account the economic value of sustainable development of the ecotourism;</p> <p>2. No utilization of traditional socio-cultural knowledge for biosphere reserve, protected area, lake, wetland etc. conservation, and its wise use;</p> <p>3. Lacks protective areas and eco-sensitive areas not listed;</p> <p>4. No education program for utilization of traditional cultural knowledge and values;</p> <p>5. No information and consultation process;</p> <p>6. No effective law enforcement;</p> <p>7. No any monitoring for the traditional social-cultural values in place;</p> <p>8. No effective control.</p>	<p>1. Taking into account of the social-cultural values and benefits of the conservation of biodiversity and wise use of the Lalzi Bay for effective utility competitive management of site and at the same time taking into account the economic value of sustainable development of the new industry, ecotourism in the Lalzi Bay;</p> <p>2. Utilization of traditional cultural knowledge for biosphere reserve or protected area, lake, wetland etc. conservation, and its wise use;</p> <p>3. Socio-cultural progress by use of utility competitive management methods towards the sustainable development of ecotourism, which recognizes the needs of everyone;</p> <p>4. Growing of former civilization; use of cultural values of regional and local communities and indigenous peoples;</p> <p>5. Grow of material value as sacred sites; taking into account of the social-cultural impact assessment of Lalzi Bay;</p> <p>6. Taking into account of the livelihood impact assessment of the Lalzi Bay etc.;</p> <p>7. Education program for</p>

<p>policies and strategies for biodiversity conservation;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Ruling Government lack understandings of the importance of conservation of the biosphere reserves, protected areas, rejuvenation of wetland, lake and marsh; Lacks investment policies; Lack of legislation for conservation of biodiversity; No conservation infrastructure. Lacks education schemes; No effective law enforcement for biodiversity conservation; No monitoring for biodiversity conservation in place; No effective control for biodiversity conservation. 	<p>biodiversity in Lalzi Bay;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Good legislation for biodiversity conservation in the biosphere reserve or protected area, wetland, lake etc. in place; Changes in policies and strategies for conservation of biodiversity; Politicians, regional and local communities understand the importance of biodiversity conservation in biosphere reserve or protected area, wetland, lake etc. and sustainable development of the ecotourism into; Full investment policy regarding the biodiversity conservation by national, regional or local government; Implementation of the utility competitive management of conservation of biodiversity in Lalzi Bay; The sustainable development of biodiversity conservation in Lalzi Bay by new mentality or new approaches to problems; Educational plans/schemes for Lalzi Bay's biodiversity conservation in place etc. Education programs for conservation of biodiversity in place; Successful information and consultation process implemented; Effective law enforcement; Monitoring for conservation of biodiversity in place; Effective control measures done. 	<p>ecotourism with fewer infrastructures;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> No sustainable development of ecotourism; No effective law enforcement for sustainable development of ecotourism; No monitoring for sustainable development of ecotourism in place and no effective control for sustainable development. 	<p>ecotourism is in normal conditions, jointed and often within flawed with real assumptions and arguments;</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Changes in policies and strategies; politicians, regional and local communities understand the importance of conservation of the biosphere reserve, protected area, wetland, lake etc. and at the same time sustainable development of the ecotourism into; Full investment policy regarding the sustainable development of ecotourism and biodiversity conservation by national, regional or local government; Implementation of the utility competitive management of ecotourism in Lalzi Bay; The sustainable development of ecotourism in Lalzi Bay by new mentality or new approaches to problems; Educational plans/schemes for Lalzi Bay's Ecotourism in place; A good role of sustainable development of ecotourism in promoting socio-culture.
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TABLE XXX
SPORADIC MANAGEMENT OF ECOTOURISM

Pre Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (earlier conditions)	Post Project Scenario at Lalzi Bay (present status)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Missing of policy and strategy of ecotourism in biosphere reserve, protected area, lake, and wetland; No investment to increase reception/accommodation capacities; Fails to attract ecotourists. The debate on sustainable development of ecotourism is patchy, disjointed and often flawed with false assumptions and arguments; Politicians and local communities need education in this regard; Low level of adventurous 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Wise use and sustainable development of the new industry, ecotourism in Lalzi Bay. Good legislation for sustainable development of ecotourism on the biosphere reserve or protected area, wetland, lake etc. in place; The debate on sustainable development of

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